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AFTER CONSTANTINE
STORIES FROM THE LATE ANTIQUE AND
EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

AFTER CONSTANTINE

STORIES FROM
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EARLY
BYZANTINE
ERA

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AFTER CONSTANTINE

STORIES FROM THE LATE ANTIQUE AND
EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

COPTIC *OSTRACA* MENTIONING MONEY

SOHAIR AHMED¹

Abstract

This paper² presents five Coptic *ostraca* (potsherds) mentioning money. The transcription (with/without translation) of two *ostraca* here has been made by Wintermute (Duke University) a long time ago, however he did not publish them and agreed to be republished by me. Also, the Museum agreed to send me both photos (of *ostraca*) and his notes. The third-fifth *ostraca* are kept in RBML and are described with a suggested summary on the international website “Papyri Info”; then it was registered under my study in 2019 and 2021. The numbers of the *ostraca* are: O. BK. Mus. X2004-287 and -198 and O.Col. 19, 489, and 500.

¹ Egyptian Assistant Professor in Coptic language, Faculty of Archaeology, Ain Shams University, Cairo-Egypt, published some Coptic documentary texts written on *ostraca* and papyri, prepared dictionaries about Professions and titles, Arabic Terms, and Food and Drink in Coptic.

² I chose these *ostraca* because this paper is part of my research project in the USA (2020-2021).

Keywords: *Bronze, Coin, Money, Ostraca, Potsherd*

The money was mentioned in many kinds of Coptic texts such as letters, contracts of sale or work, accounts, loan contracts, orders for payment, and tax receipts or other kinds of receipts. The Copts preferred to write their legal/financial texts on potsherds to keep the writing longer and to be difficult to falsify.³

The Coptic texts mentioned many kinds of coins; from gold such as *holokottinos* (Lat. *solidus*) and *termesion* (Lat. *tremis*), silver coins such as kite (Egy. *qd*) and *sateere* (Lat. *stater*), and bronze-like *kas /keratse* (Lat. *carat*), and *tba* (Lat. *Myriad*); it is remarkable that the name of the coin was mentioned in different forms in Coptic texts and it was either similar or different from its Latin or Greek name. Furthermore, the coins were changed in their weight and value from one time to another.⁴

Coinage in Egypt

During the Pharaonic Period, the people bartered their crops and cattle amongst themselves to obtain necessary commodities. In the 30th Dynasty, the Egyptians used a coin called *nwb-nfr* (beautiful/good gold), to pay the Greek mercenary soldiers who helped to fight the Persians and used also in transactions with foreign merchants, but the ancient Egyptians had not yet adopted a

³ Cf. O. Cairo Mus. no. 19, 20.

⁴ Ahmed 2017, p. 22; Ahmed 2020, pp. 53-58.

monetary trade system of their own and they still used the bartering system.⁵

In Greco-Roman Egypt, the coins were used in markets and also minted in Alexandria (the capital of Egypt at that time); the Alexandrian mint produced coinage throughout the Ptolemaic period and during the Roman era until 296 CE. In fact, Alexandrian coins continued to be used as the main currency in Egypt during Roman rule, alongside the Roman coins. The majority of coins were made of bronze. There were also gold, copper and silver coins.⁶ Egypt had a separate coinage system from the rest of the Roman Empire from Augustus conquest of Egypt until Diocletian's monetary reforms of 294/6. Thereafter, it was incorporated into the Roman monetary systems. By the fifth century, the coins available in Egypt included the gold *solidus*, *semissis* (half *solidus*), and *tremissis* (third of a *solidus*), as well as the bronze coins (some scholars refer to them as copper, others as bronze) especially *folles* and *nummi* of in various sizes. In addition, the Egyptians used two other monetary denominations: the *talent* and the *myriad*. Silver coinage was available in other parts of the Empire but that is rarely attested in Egypt.⁷ In Islamic Egypt, there was the Arabization of some coins like the Roman

⁵ Hawas et al. 2010, p. 15.

⁶ Escoffey 2012, p. 35.

⁷ Buchanan 2015, p. 11,19.

solidus which became *Dinar* and the Greek *drachma* which became *Dirham*, also entered the Arabic small coin called *Kharrobah* (lit. carob-pod) known in Egypt, but I observe that the majority of coins were still known in the Islamic period with their Greek/Latin names.⁸ The Copts kept their money in jars made of pottery which contained usually the gold coins.⁹

Signs for publishing¹⁰

[abc] Letters are missing from the original text due to lacuna, restored by the editor.

a(bc) Abbreviation / symbol in the text, expanded by the editor.

<ab> Characters erroneously omitted by the ancient scribe, restored or corrected by the editor.

{ab} Letters in the text considered erroneous and superfluous by the editor.

\ab/ Letters added above the line of writing.

... letters difficult to read by the editor

Dialects¹¹: A Akhmimic; B Bohairic; F Fayumic; L Lycopolitan; M Oxyrhynchite; S Sahidic

⁸ Ahmed 2020, p. 53, 57.

⁹ See Ahmed 2020, p.51 and the photos here.

¹⁰ Cromwell 2017, p. xxiii.

¹¹ Allen 2020, p. 125.

Ostrakon 1

Potsherd NO. X2004-287

Content by Wintermute: Not Written

Content by me: A private letter, the sender asked for a sum of money will be given to a man called Dios when he delivered this letter. This sum represents 20 bronze coins called *she*.

Recto

1. ⲧⲉⲣⲉⲗⲓⲟⲥ ⲙⲁⲕⲁⲣⲓ
 2. ⲛⲓ ⲧⲉⲓⲃⲗⲗⲉ ⲛⲁⲕ
 3. ⲧⲁⲭⲟⲩⲧ ⲛⲱⲉ ⲛⲁⲕ
1. ⲧⲉⲣⲉⲗⲓⲟⲥ (the son of) Makari
 2. brings this potsherd to you

3. give twenty *she* to him

1.1 Coptic has a number of meanings, expressing a real condition. The Second Present is often used in this function¹².

μακαρι: A personal name, written also as μακαρε, μακαρη, μακαρα, μακαρμακαρια, μακαριος,¹³ is common in Greek as *Makarios*, which is used also in Coptic as the title means “blessed, late” for deceased persons from Egyptian origin¹⁴ and according to the context where it cannot be a title, as suggested by Wintermute.

1.2 τεϊ in AFMS Dialects, B as θαι-, L αστεει, it is unstressed form of demonstrative pronouns which is appended as a construct prefix to nouns.¹⁵

1.3 χογτ written in the compound form χογτ- perhaps as a mistake and the right here should be χογωτ.¹⁶

ωε: the smallest coin is known in Coptic only and no Greek equivalent for it, lit means “lit wood.” I think the name of this coin relating to consideration the wood is less than metal and wood refers also to the cross perhaps there was a cross printed on this

¹² Allen 2020, p. 79.

¹³ Koptisch Namen, p.57b -58a.

¹⁴ Mentioned as (*ma'-kherw*).

¹⁵ Allen 2020, p.20.

¹⁶ Allen 2020, p. 120, *Coptic Dictionary online*. Available at: copticdictionary.org [Last access 23/11/2021].

coin, it was made of bronze and equals 1/10 or 1/12 of carat.¹⁷ Cromwell mentioned this coin as a denomination bronze coin with between 240 and 288 *she* to one *holkottinos* (solidus).¹⁸

Ostrakon 2

Potsherd NO. X2004-198

Content by Wintermute: Not Written

Content by me: Order for payment or an account, it includes number of coins of little charge, as (*nummi*, *carat* and *myriad*) will be given to some people.

Recto

1. †πατερε [ϣεζαι ἡNN?]

¹⁷ Ahmed 2020, p. 57.

¹⁸ Cromwell 2017, p. xxiii.

2. εἰς χοῦτσνο [οὐσῆνοῦμ-]
3. οὐς οὐκας ἦ [NNἠη?]
4. [οὐ?]τβα ἦπιναζ[]
5. []ναἰ χ<ε> εἰς[]

1. †Pater[he writes to NN]
2. Here is, twenty two [of Numm-]
3. us (with?) one carat to[NN and ?]
4. [one?] myriad to Pinax[]
5. [...]....and here is[.....]

1.1 Cf. the personal name: πατερperhaps as var. of πατηρ¹⁹ which is from Greek origin and means “father.”

1.2 εἰς behold, here is' an initial particle introduces nouns and Coptic statements²⁰ and I suggest it as a particle for paying attention became now in common Egyptian Arabic as *boss* means “look” and also still known with the meaning as *khallyballak* in common Arabic means “behold, take care.”

There is ligature in the letters of this word in this line and in the last line.

¹⁹ Hasitzka 2007, p. 72a, 71b.

²⁰ Allen 2020, p. 28.

l.3[.]ⲟϥ suggest it to ⲃⲛⲟϥⲙⲟϥ as the coin called *nummus*.²¹

ⲕⲁⲥ: means lit. “bone” refers to “carat” as coin= 1/24 of solidus,²² a division of the principal gold coin with 24 carats to one *solidus* (*holokottinos*) as bronze coin²³ but sometimes mentioned from gold, Latin as *Keratum* equal approx. 0.189 gm. I think choosing this term “bone” referring to this coin in Coptic relating to the link (or the concept) between the bones of the God and the silver in ancient Egypt²⁴ for that the bones may be associated with the silver which was used mainly for making coins,²⁵ however the carat was never made from silver! However, the word silver in Coptic refers to the money in general.²⁶

l.4 ⲧⲃⲁ'ten-thousand' —AS ⲧⲃⲁ, ⲃⲞⲃⲟ, Ⲣⲧⲃⲉ, (usually an indefinite large number), ⲃⲓⲧⲧⲃⲁ'half-ten thousand' (=5000)²⁷.In

²¹ *Coptic Dictionary Online*. Available at: coptic-dictionary.org [Last access 23/11/2021]; Ahmed 2020, p. 54.

²² CED, p. 63.

²³ Cromwell 2017, p. xxii.

²⁴ Cf. the bones of the sun god Re became silver when he became old in the myth “Destruction of mankind” known in the Dynastic period.

²⁵ Ahmed 2020, p. 54.

²⁶ *Ibid.* 2020, p. 57.

²⁷ *Ibid.* 2020, p. 26.

Latin as myriad, used as coin in Coptic.²⁸ The myriad equaled ten thousand denarius in the fourth century or six and two-thirds talents. By the mid-sixth century, one gold solidus equaled twenty Roman pounds (approximately 328 grams each) of bronze or 48,000 talents or 4,800 myriads.²⁹

ⲡⲏⲛⲁⲛⲓ may be the same personal name written as ⲡⲏⲛⲁⲕ/,³⁰ the word *pinakis* means in Greek “small tablet.”³¹ No assimilation for ⲛ before this word perhaps the text is from Middle Egypt.

ⲓ.ⲛ ⲛⲁⲓ: Perhaps represents end of the personal name ⲁⲡⲓⲁⲧⲛⲁⲓⲟⲣ ⲡⲁⲡⲁⲧⲛⲁⲓ³² or represents the dative means “to me”.

ⲭⲉⲛⲉⲓⲥ: written the two *epsilons* in two words as one epsilon was very common,³³ as diphthong.

ⲭⲉ: conjunction means “that”³⁴ or ‘saying’,³⁵ but I observed that it means sometimes “and;”³⁶ this expression ⲭⲉⲓⲥ usually written before numbers either of money or of measures or of sacks.³⁷

²⁸ *Ibid.* 2020, p. 56.

²⁹ Buchanan 2015, p. 19.

³⁰ Hasitzka 2007, p. 79b.

³¹ *Coptic Dictionary Online*. Available at: coptic-dictionary.org [Last access 23/11/2021].

³² Hasitzka 2007, p.70b,72a.

³³ Ahmed 2020, p.45.

³⁴ *Coptic Dictionary Online*. Available at: coptic-dictionary.org [Last access 23/11/2021].

³⁵ P. Sarga, nos 187, 188.

Ostrakon 3

O. Columbia no. 19

Date: AD 500 – 699

Provenance: Memnoneia-Djeme-Thebes

Dimension: 9 x 14.5 cm

Content: perhaps the end of a letter? That mentions Victor and 30 something.³⁸

Content & summary on the
website:

Letter?

*Perhaps the end of a letter that mentions
Victor and 30 something.*³⁹

Content by me: Receipt of money, the text recorded paying 6 of bronze coins called *she*⁴⁰ as apart from the total sum of 30 she-coins. The name Victor remains and perhaps represents the payer or the name of his father. The beginning of receipt is complete but the text after the name Victor is lost here. I believe it is not tax receipt because the payment is not in gold coins (or even in carats).

³⁶ Ahmed 2020, p. 44.

³⁷ See: P. Sarga, nos. 187,188.

³⁸ Available at: <http://papyri.info/apis/columbia.apis.19> [Last access 23/11/2021].

³⁹ Available at: <http://papyri.info/apis/columbia.apis.19> [Last access 22/11/2021].

⁴⁰ For this coin, see *ostrakon* no.1 here.

And suggest this text represented receiving of repayment a loan⁴¹ or perhaps the interest (usually the loan was for gold coins and sometimes the interest was in bronze coins such as *talent* and *myriad*).⁴²

Recto

1. εις σοου νωε
2. αγει ετοτ εμπαδδ
3. νωε [ντοκ?...]ρε[...]ροσ νικ
4. τωρ []

⁴¹ Cf. a loan contract for 40 she- coins in: O. Crum ST, no. 93.

⁴² Buchanan 2015, p. 72.

Content by me: beginning of letter addressed to monastic superior concerning sending certain numbers (missed in the text) of *she* -coin of bronze to someone is missed in the text.

Recto

1. ϣ̅ ϣ̅INE ε[TEKHNTEI-]
2. ΩT εT[TAIHY (/ OYAAV) APH ΠNA]
3. NΓ̅T̅N̅[NOOY...N]
4. ΩE [N̅ZOMNT]
5.[]

1. ϣ̅I greet [your fatherhood]
2. the [reverend/ holy] , do favor

3. And se[nd (number) of]
4. *she* [of bronze]
- 5.to?[.....]

Ostrakon 5

O. Columbia no. 500

Date: AD 500 – 690

Provenance: unknown

Dimension: 5.6 x 7.2 cm

Content: beginning of a letter possibly written by [Ky]ros.⁴⁷

Content by me: beginning of a letter concerning sending or paying one half (of solidus as a gold coin) to someone called Mena.

⁴⁷ Available at: <http://papyri.info/apis/columbia.apis.19> [Last access 23/11/2021].

Recto

1. [Ⲡ ⲡⲉⲧ]ⲣⲟⲥ ⲉϥⲥⲁⲓ [ⲚⲚⲚ]
 2. [ⲁ]ⲣⲓ ⲧⲁⲕⲁⲡⲏ [Ⲛⲓⲭⲟⲟϥ]
 3. [ⲟ]ϥⲡⲏⲱⲉ [Ⲛⲁⲟⲗⲟⲕ/?]
 4. [ⲙ]ⲙⲉⲛⲁ [.....]
-
1. [Ⲡⲡⲉⲧ]ⲣⲟⲥ who writes [to NN]
 2. [D]o charity [and send]
 3. [one] half [of solidus]
 4. [to] Mena [.....]

1.2 ϭⲟⲟϥ ⲟⲩ ⲧⲚⲚⲟϥⲟⲩ.⁴⁸

1.3 ⲟϥⲡⲏⲱⲉ: mentioned referring to (ⲟϥⲡⲏⲱⲉ Ⲛⲁⲟⲗⲟⲕ/) “half of the solidus.”⁴⁹Worth about 12 carats, mentioned in a Coptic contract from the 7th century as a wage of a farmer and worth in this text 11 1/2 carats.⁵⁰

Summary of Texts:

This paper presents five Coptic texts mentioning money/coins as follows:

⁴⁸ See the previous text.

⁴⁹ Crum, *Copt. Dict.*, 278a; O. Crum ST, no. 437.

⁵⁰ CPR IV, no.166.

- A private letter includes asking for delivery 20 *she*-bronze coins by the letter carrier.
- Apart from the order of payment or an account mentioned coins made of bronze as *nummus*, *carat*, and *myriad* to be given to certain persons.
- A receipt of receiving six *she*-coins as a part or an installment of total of 30 *she*.
- Beginning of a letter including a request for sending a number of *she*-coins.
- Beginning of a letter including a request for sending/paying half *solidus*.

Conclusions

- The coins used in Late Antique Egypt were of various origins like Egyptian, Greek, Roman, and Arabic. And they were minted from gold, silver, bronze, or copper with remarks that the silver coins were rare in the Coptic texts relating to daily life especially in the 6th- 8th centuries CE.
- The money of little charge (low value) was minted from either bronze or copper. The coins mentioned in this paper were minted mainly from bronze except the half-solidus which was minted from gold.

- According to texts, The Copts used the gold coins mainly in paying: taxes, loans, penalties/fines, salaries (of some officials, farmers, or carpenters), and prices (for cattle and large quantities of some goods) while the bronze coins were used also in prices (such as sheets of papyri/ parchment and cereals), wages (of some workers) and in loan's interest.
- The Copts usually described the gold coin in the texts as “good” or “pure and without fraude”, or mentioned its value (in carats), but they didn’t write that for the bronze coins.
- The *she*-coin is Egyptian, appeared in Coptic texts only means “lit wood”, but it was made of bronze, the cross means also (in Coptic) *she*, so it may represent a bronze coin with a cross printed on its side. The Copts always asked for sending it in many texts; it is mentioned usually in the texts from Thebes in the 7th/8th c. CE. For that, I can suggest the date of *ostraca* from the same period.

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Fig. 1. - the 1st coin known in Egypt and called *nwb-nfr*

(Hawas et al. 2010, p19)

Fig.2. - A jar contained 171 gold coins, from a church in Middle Egypt,
Cairo Museum
(Hawas et al. 2010, p. 34)

Fig. 3. - *Dinar, Solidus and Tremis* from the Museum of Bibliotheque
Alexandrina (T. by me)

Fig. 4. - Clear photo for ostracon no.2, sent by the BK Museum

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